

A TEST FOR INVESTIGATING DELAMINATION MIGRATION IN COMPOSITE TAPE LAMINATES

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1 Introduction

Delamination cracking is a failure mode commonly associated with composite tape laminates, and has thus received considerable attention in the academic community. Much of this focus, however, has involved the consideration of delamination as a separate mode of failure. For instance, considerable effort has been paid toward characterizing individual delamination, driven under mode-I, mode-II, mode-III and a mixture of these loading conditions [1-4]. Meanwhile, analysis methods have been developed that allow for the possibility of simulating delamination onset and growth [5, 6]. The overall trend has been for analyses to allow for simulation of delamination growth along one particular ply interface without the possibility for migration of that delamination to another interface. While such analyses are adequate in many situations, delamination growth in laminates commonly involves migration between different ply interfaces [7-10]. In response to this situation, methods are being developed to enable simulation of such migration events [11, 12]. Experimental work has also focused on investigating delamination migration in laminates and has typically utilized tests that involve multiple migration events [9, 13]. More recently, a test method was developed that was designed to characterize delamination migration for the purpose of providing benchmarking data for validation of analyses for simulating migration [14]. The associated specimen, depicted in Fig. 1, is a cross ply laminate with a mid-plane insert spanning part way along the specimen length. The specimen is loaded in such a manner as to first cause onset of delamination growth from the insert front followed by migration of this delamination to another ply interface within the specimen. Overall, the delamination growth and migration events occur uniformly across the specimen width and thus the test yields data against which 2-dimensional

analyses could be validated. One issue with the test is that delamination growth onset and migration tend to be unstable events, which makes the act of simulating the test for validation purposes more cumbersome. The purpose of the work described here was to modify the stacking sequence of this delamination migration test specimen in order to promote stable delamination growth and migration. To this end, a series of analyses were conducted in order to determine an appropriate specimen stacking sequence. Specimens were subsequently manufactured and tested.

2 Materials and Methods

The composite material selected for this investigation was an IM7/8552 carbon/epoxy tape. Two-dimensional finite element analyses of delamination migration specimens made from this material were performed. The crack closure method was used to compute the energy release rate G_T (and its components G_I and G_{II}) for a set of fixed delamination lengths. Following [15], the critical load and displacement for each crack length was obtained by linearly scaling the prescribed displacements and load:

$$P_{crit} = P \sqrt{\frac{G_c}{G_T}}, \quad \delta_{crit} = \delta \sqrt{\frac{G_c}{G_T}} \quad (1)$$

where critical energy release rate G_c was assumed to be given by a mixed mode exponential law. The resultant critical load-displacement curve was then used to assess the stability of each candidate layup, under displacement-control conditions. Additionally, for each stacking sequence, the specimen bending-twist coupling and its ability to withstand the expected load levels were also assessed.

3 Results

The nature of stability of delamination growth up to the migration onset was evaluated from the finite element analyses of the migration test. An example result is shown in Fig. 2, which is a plot of applied force, P versus load-point displacement, δ . The plot compares the critical load-displacement responses of the original (OR) [14] and of the redesigned stacking sequence (S0). For the case considered in Fig. 2, the original stacking sequence shows unstable delamination growth under displacement-controlled conditions. This finding is in agreement with the nature of the delamination observed in actual specimens [14]. On the contrary, the redesigned layout shows stable delamination under displacement-controlled loading, as intended. Complementary analysis also showed that the bending-twist coupling of the redesigned layup was of the same order of magnitude of the original layup [14], and that it was capable of withstanding the expected load range, confirming its suitability for testing.

Tests performed on actual migration specimens with the stacking sequence selected as a result of the current study (shown in Fig. 1) confirmed that delamination growth onset in these specimens is stable.

4 Conclusions

With respect to the main aim of the current study, a stacking sequence was identified that would promote stable delamination growth onset and migration in the delamination migration test specimen. Data from tests on these specimens are compiled in order to provide a means of comparison with analyses designed for simulating delamination migration in composite tape laminates.

Fig. 1. Schematic of the delamination migration specimen

Fig. 2. Comparison between the critical load-displacement response of the original layup (OR) and of the redesigned layup (S0). The unstable region of OR under displacement-controlled conditions, is highlighted.

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